

POSSIBLE ANTIAMOEBCIC AGENTS. PART VI. SYNTHESSES OF
SOME SUBSTITUTED DIALKYLAMINO-TRIMETHYLENE-
BENZYLAMINES AND THEIR DICHLOROACETATES

By A. B. SEN AND YASHWANT D. KULKARNI

Several substituted dialkylamino-trimethylene-benzylamines, structurally related to cleavage products of the emetine molecule, and their dichloroacetates have been synthesised with a view to testing their antiamebic activity.

Several attempts have been made to obtain compounds structurally related to emetine (I), eliminating the side effects while retaining or enhancing the amoebicidal activity of the alkaloid, with the belief that somewhere in the structure of emetine lies the site of activity. Pioneering work on these lines has been done by Pynan *et al.* (*Chem. & Ind.*, 1937, 55, 789). Goodson and Goodwin (*Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1948, 3, 44, 49, 62), Sugasawa (*J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1949, 69, 8) and Osbond (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 3464) have helped to clarify the pharmacophore responsible for the activity of this class of compounds. The activity of emetine is attributed to the presence of two nitrogen centres, of which one is secondary and the other, tertiary, separated by a carbon chain. This prompted the authors to prepare several dialkylamino-polymethylene-benzylamines (II) containing the conventional two nitrogen centres, one secondary and other tertiary, with a view to studying their amoebicidal activity.

The present paper deals with the syntheses of γ -dialkylamino-trimethylene-benzylamines (II: R' and R'' = chloro, hydroxy and methoxy groups; $n=3$; $R_1 = R_2$ = piperidino, morpholino or diethylamino groups).

Surrey *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2214; 1955, 77, 3798, 5403) have observed significant amoebicidal activity in several *N*-benzyl-*N*-hydroxyalkyl-dichloroacetamides (III), obtained by dichloroacetylation of *N*-hydroxy-alkylbenzylamines. We have also dichloro-acetylated the diamines (II) to study the change in the amoebicidal activity of the resulting compounds (IV)

The diamines (II) were obtained by one of the following methods: (i) condensation of substituted benzyl bromides with γ -dialkylamino-*n*-propylamines or (ii) condensation of equimolar quantities of substituted benzaldehydes with γ -dialkylamino-*n*-propylamines, followed by catalytic hydrogenation of the Schiff bases in ethanol in presence of platinum oxide.

γ -Dialkylamino-*n*-propylamines were prepared by the condensation of secondary amides with an excess of acrylonitrile (Whitmore, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 727), followed by high pressure (500 lbs./sq. inch) hydrogenation of the resulting nitriles in absolute methanol, saturated with dry ammonia, in the presence of Raney nickel.

The amines (II), which were all liquids (except those derived from 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzaldehyde), were purified by distilling under reduced pressure and characterized through their picrates. The dichloroacetates (IV) of these amines were obtained by following the method of Surrey *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The benzaldehydes (viz., 2-chloro-3:4-dimethoxy- and 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-) were prepared by the methods given in the literature and benzyl bromides (viz., 4-chloro- and 2:4-dichloro-) were obtained by the side-chain bromination of the corresponding chlorotoluenes using benzoyl peroxide as catalyst (Schnid and Karrer, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1946, **29**, 573).

β -Dialkylaminopropionitriles.— β -Piperidino-, β -morpholino- and β -diethylaminopropionitriles were prepared according to the method of Whitmore (*loc. cit.*). A brief account of the preparation of β -piperidinopropionitrile is given below.

Piperidine (46 g., 0.5M) was added to 50 g. of cold acrylonitrile (0.95M). The mixture was refluxed for one hour on a water-bath and then allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. Excess of acrylonitrile was removed and the residue was distilled under reduced pressure, b. p. 128-30°/30 mm, yield 97%. In a similar manner β -morpholinopropionitrile, b. p. 120-21°/2 mm (93%) and β -diethylaminopropionitrile, b. p. 196-98°/760 mm (94%), were prepared.

*γ -Piperidino-*n*-propylamine.*—The above three β -dialkylaminopropionitriles were subjected to reductive amination to yield the corresponding γ -dialkylamino-*n*-propylamine. The preparation of γ -piperidino-*n*-propylamine is given below.

Absolute methanol (250 g.) was cooled in an ice-salt mixture and dry ammonia gas was bubbled till about 90 g. (3.6M) was absorbed. This ammoniacal methyl alcohol

was placed in the pressure hydrogenator vessel, with β -piperidinopropionitrile (51 g., 0.4M) and Raney nickel catalyst (35 g., 0.6M).

The nitrile was reduced under a hydrogen pressure of 500-550 lbs./sq. in. with stirring for 3 to 4 hours. The uptake of hydrogen was very rapid and was mostly completed within the first hour. After the reduction, the reaction mixture was filtered to remove the catalyst and about 25-30 c.c. of the solvent was carefully distilled to remove gaseous ammonia. It was then cooled in an ice-salt bath and saturated with dry HCl gas. Methyl alcohol was then distilled off under reduced pressure leaving behind a pasty residue of γ -piperidino-*n*-propylamine hydrochloride and ammonium chloride. The salt was then carefully decomposed by the slow addition of 70% NaOH solution, when two distinct layers of liquids separated. The upper layer consisting of the required amine was collected and dried over KOH pellets. The crude amine, after carefully drying over sodium wire, was distilled under reduced pressure, b. p. 88°/1 mm, yield 72.4%. Whitmore (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 7127) reported b. p. 205°/733 mm and yield 68.5%.

Picrate.—On mixing hot alcoholic solutions of amine (0.25 g.) and picric acid (0.25 g.), a yellow turbidity was observed, which on cooling and scratching deposited a yellow picrate, m. p. 208-209° (decomp). Whitmore (*loc. cit.*) reported m. p. 208°.

*γ -Morpholino-*n*-propylamine*.—Proceeding in a similar manner with β -morpholinopropionitrile (52.5 g.), γ -morpholino-*n*-propylamine, b. p. 92-3°/1 mm, was obtained, yield 37.4 g. (65%). Whitmore (*loc. cit.*) reported b. p. 219°/733 mm and yield 60%. Picrate m. p. 165°, reported m. p. 166°.

*γ -Diethylamino-*n*-propylamine*.—Starting from γ -diethylaminopropionitrile (63 g.) and following the same procedure, γ -diethylamino-*n*-propylamine, b. p. 170-75°, was obtained in 40 g. yield (61%). Whitmore (*loc. cit.*) reported b. p. 168°/730 mm and yield 54%. Picrate m. p. 195-96°, reported m. p. 195°.

*Method (a): Condensation of 2:4-Dichlorobenzyl Bromide with γ -Piperidino-*n*-propylamine*.—2:4-Dichlorobenzyl bromide (3.6 g., 0.015M) was added dropwise to vigorously stirred γ -piperidino-*n*-propylamine (6.3 g., 0.045M) without any external cooling. After the addition was complete, the stirring of the reaction mixture was continued for an hour and then allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. It was then poured with stirring into a large volume of water and the semisolid separating was extracted with chloroform. The organic layer, on careful drying over anhydrous potassium carbonate, was concentrated to give a viscous red liquid which was purified by reduced pressure distillation, b. p. 193-95°/2 mm, yield 3.5 g. (64%). Found: N, 9.20. $C_{15}H_{22}N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 9.30%.

*Method (b): Condensation of *o*-Chlorobenzaldehyde and γ -Morpholino-*n*-propylamine*.—A mixture of *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde (2.82 g., 0.02M) and γ -morpholino-*n*-propylamine (3.25 g., 0.02M) was heated in vacuo over a steam-bath for 2 hours. The Schiff base was dissolved in hot ethyl alcohol (50 c.c.) and the hot solution was catalytically hydrogenated (over 0.25 g. of platinum oxide) for 5 hours at 60 lbs./sq. in.

It was then filtered to remove the catalyst, the filtrate was concentrated and the brown residue subjected to reduced pressure distillation, b. p. 192-93°/2 mm, yield 5.6 g. (91%). (Found: N, 10.27. $C_{14}H_{21}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 10.43%).

The various diamines (II), prepared by the above methods, along with their picrates are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
[Vide structure II]

R' and R''	B. P.	% Yield.	Mol. formula.	% Nitrogen.		Picrates		
				Found.	Calc.	M. P.	Mol. formula.	% Nitrogen. Found. Calc.
R ₁ = R ₂ = piperidyl-								
2-Chloro-	183-84°/2 mm	62	C ₁₅ H ₂₇ N ₂ Cl	10.42	10.51	200-201°	C ₂₁ H ₃₈ O ₇ N ₅ Cl	13.94 14.13
4-Chloro-	193-95°/2	58	C ₁₅ H ₂₇ N ₂ Cl	10.44	10.51	133-34°	C ₂₁ H ₃₈ O ₇ N ₅ Cl	14.00 14.13
2:4-Dichloro-	195-97°/7	64	C ₁₆ H ₂₉ N ₂ Cl ₂	9.20	9.30	180-81°	C ₂₁ H ₃₈ O ₇ N ₅ Cl	13.01 13.21
2-Hydroxy-5-chloro-	*137°	55	C ₁₅ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	9.63	9.91	188-89°	C ₂₁ H ₃₁ O ₈ N ₅ Cl	13.63 13.68
3:4-Dimethoxy-	218-20°/20	72	C ₁₇ H ₂₉ O ₂ N ₂	9.36	9.59	195-96°	C ₂₇ H ₃₁ O ₈ N ₅	13.12 13.43
R ₁ and R ₂ = morpholinyl-								
2-Chloro-	192-93°/2	91	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ ON ₂ Cl	10.27	10.43	203-204°	C ₂₀ H ₂₉ O ₈ N ₅ Cl	14.12 14.08
4-Chloro-	207-209°/2	71	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ ON ₂ Cl	10.27	10.43	128-29°	C ₂₀ H ₂₉ O ₈ N ₅ Cl	13.86 14.08
2:4-Dichloro-	163-65°/2	76	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂	9.14	9.24	188-89°	C ₂₀ H ₂₉ O ₈ N ₅ Cl ₂	13.00 13.16
2-Hydroxy-5-chloro-	*140°	61	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	9.54	9.84	208-209°	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₉ N ₅ Cl	13.43 13.63
3:4-Dimethoxy-	250-52°/20	68	C ₁₆ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂	9.31	9.52	222°	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₁₀ N ₅	13.28 13.38
R ₁ and R ₂ = diethylamino-								
2-Chloro-	166-67°/2	77	C ₁₄ H ₂₃ N ₂ Cl	10.96	11.00	143-44°	C ₂₀ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₅ Cl	14.58 14.48
4-Chloro-	169-70°/2	65	C ₁₄ H ₂₃ N ₂ Cl	10.98	11.00	130-31°	C ₂₀ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₅ Cl	14.52 14.48
2:4-Dichloro-	181-82°/3	93	C ₁₄ H ₂₃ N ₂ Cl ₂	9.43	9.69	133-34°	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ O ₇ N ₅ Cl ₂	13.42 13.52
2-Hydroxy-5-chloro-	*109°	58	C ₁₄ H ₂₃ ON ₂ Cl	10.33	10.35	168-60°	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ O ₈ N ₅ Cl	14.13 14.02
3:4-Dimethoxy-	173-74°/1	92	C ₁₆ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂	9.91	10.00	152-53°	C ₂₂ H ₃₁ O ₈ N ₅	13.45 13.75

* Denotes the m.p. of the solids.

Dichloroacetates (IV) of the Diamines.—These were obtained by following the method of Surrey (*loc.cit.*). The synthesis of *N*-(2:4-dichlorobenzyl)-*N*-(γ -piperidinotrimethylene)-dichloroacetamide is given below.

Dichloroacetyl chloride (0.75 g., 0.005M) in dichloroethane (3 c.c.) was added gradually with stirring to a mixture of γ -piperidinotrimethylene-(2:4 dichloro)-benzylamine (1.5 g., 0.005M) in dichloroethane (10 c.c.) and 1N-NaOH (5 c.c.). The temperature was kept below 0° with external cooling. The reaction mixture was allowed to come to the room temperature with stirring and the organic layer was separated. It was washed successively with 1N-NaOH, water, 1N-HCl and water and then dried over potassium carbonate. The residue obtained after removing dichloroethane by distillation was recrystallised from absolute alcohol-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 163-64°, yield 1.1 g. (53.5%). (Found: N, 6.71. $C_{17}H_{23}ON_2Cl_2$ requires N, 6.79%). Five dichloroacetates, prepared by following the above method, are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

R' & R''	R.	M. P.	% Yield.	Mol. formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
4-Chloro-	γ -Piperidino-trimethylene	111°	53.0	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{22}\text{ON}_2\text{Cl}_4$	7.31	7.42
2:4-Dichloro- Do	Do	163-64°	53.5	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{22}\text{ON}_2\text{Cl}_4$	6.71	6.79
	γ -Morpholino-trimethylene	173°	36.2	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_4$	6.51	6.77
Do	γ -Diethylamino-trimethylene	139°	40.0	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{ON}_2\text{Cl}_4$	6.60	7.00
2-Hydroxy- 5-chloro-	β -Hydroxy-ethylene	147°	43.0	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}_3$	4.51	4.48

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY, LUCKNOW.

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